

ISic1510

I.Sicily inscription 1510

Language

Punic

Type

building (?)

Material

tuff

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Temple C

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645011

Bibliography

Amadasi Guzzo, M.G. 1967. Le iscrizioni fenicie e puniche delle colonie in Occidente. Rome. At Sic.Pun.08

Garbini, G 1967. Catalogo delle iscrizioni fenicie conservate nel Museo Archeologico Nazionale di Palermo. *Kokalos*. 13: 66-72. At 68 no.4 undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 602-603

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